

LASSO: Accurate and Efficient Detection of Long-Lived Sparse Items in High-Speed Data Streams

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Abstract

In high-speed data streams, identifying long-lived (also referred to as *persistent*) sparse items is critical, as such patterns may indicate stealthy or low-rate threats yet remain largely underexplored. Although recent studies have begun to examine this problem, existing approaches either suffer from low lookup accuracy due to coarse update strategies or rely on complex data structures with costly update operations, overlooking the practical requirement of deployability. These limitations hinder scalability, particularly as programmable switches and FPGAs are increasingly adopted as data-processing substrates that sustain high-speed processing under strict resource and operational constraints. To address these challenges, we propose LASSO, a lightweight and hardware-conscious approach that achieves high detection accuracy under tight memory budgets while sustaining high processing throughput on industry-grade hardware, including Tofino-1 programmable switches and FPGA platforms. LASSO leverages the observation that long-lived sparse items exhibit a small gap between persistence and frequency, evicting items with large deviations to prioritize promising candidates. In addition, LASSO incorporates fine-grained, temporally aware protection to prevent long-lived items from being prematurely displaced by abundant short-lived items in highly skewed data streams. We further develop a formal analytical model to establish the theoretical soundness of LASSO. Extensive evaluations across CPU, Tofino, and FPGA platforms demonstrate that LASSO delivers high accuracy and throughput while operating within strict resource constraints.

CCS Concepts

• Information systems → Data stream mining.

Keywords

Data stream processing, approximate data structures, programmable switch, FPGA

1 Introduction

Detecting long-lived sparse items in high-speed data streams, which persist over extended periods despite low activity levels, is essential due to their significance in many practical applications [6, 23, 31]. For example, data exfiltration attacks may distribute their activity over time by intermittently transmitting small amounts of sensitive

information, blending into background traffic rather than generating noticeable bursts. Similar long-lived sparse patterns also appear in data mining and user behavior analysis, where anomalous accounts remain active for long durations while generating only sporadic actions, such as occasional logins, clicks, or transactions, making them difficult to distinguish from benign low-activity users.

Despite its importance, identifying items that exhibit long-lived sparse behavior remains highly challenging. Modern data streams arrive at massive scale and high speed, making it impractical to maintain per-item state or perform fine-grained tracking for all observed items [17, 28]. Moreover, practical deployment environments impose stringent resource constraints. Large-scale data processing systems must operate within very limited fast memory, such as on-chip CPU caches (e.g., L1 cache) [20], while emerging programmable devices further restrict available computation and storage resources [37]. In addition, real-world data streams typically exhibit highly skewed item distributions, where the majority of items are short-lived, while only a small fraction persist over time [16, 17, 36]. Among these persistent items, many exhibit high frequency, which further complicates the task of isolating and preserving long-lived sparse items.

► **Limitations of Existing Approaches.** To cope with these challenges, approximate data structures, often known as *sketches*, have been widely adopted for processing high-speed data streams [5, 7–9, 13, 24, 26, 30, 35]. Existing sketch-based solutions predominantly target heavy-based item detection, such as identifying heavy hitters with high frequency [11, 19, 20, 22, 34]. In contrast, long-lived sparse items remain largely unexplored and differ fundamentally from heavy items.

Although several approaches have been proposed to identify long-lived sparse items [6, 23, 31], as discussed in Section 2.3, existing methods still exhibit several key limitations. First, some approaches [6] employ simple weighting mechanisms to track candidate items without explicitly capturing the characteristics of long-lived sparse behavior (as elaborated in Section 3.1). As a result, their detection accuracy degrades significantly, particularly under tight memory budgets [31]. Second, to improve detection accuracy, more recent methods [31] adopt multi-stage designs that first filter potential non-candidates and then track long-lived sparse items in subsequent stages. While effective in reducing interference, these designs introduce more complex update logic and additional processing overhead, which limits achievable throughput. Third,

practical deployability on constrained hardware remains largely overlooked. In high-speed environments, programmable switches and Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) are increasingly used as data-processing substrates [16, 19, 32, 37], yet their execution models enforce stringent constraints on both computation and memory, *especially on programmable switches* [32]. Consequently, the complexity of existing approaches severely limits their practical deployability.

► **Our Approach.** To achieve high lookup accuracy, fast processing speed, and broad compatibility with constrained practical hardware, we propose a novel mechanism, LASSO. *To the best of our knowledge, LASSO is the first approach for long-lived sparse item lookup that maintains reliable performance at high data rates on a production-grade programmable switch.* To meet these goals, LASSO adopts an elegant yet effective design. A key observation is that long-lived sparse items exhibit only a small gap between their frequency and persistence. LASSO leverages this property by monitoring the deviation between these two metrics and using it as a replacement criterion when hash collisions occur. Items with large deviations are considered unlikely long-lived sparse candidates and are promptly evicted, allowing limited memory resources to be reserved for more promising items. This design enhances both detection accuracy and memory efficiency. To further protect long-lived items, LASSO incorporates temporal information from item arrivals. Inspired by [14], we observe that long-lived items typically experience fewer absent time windows than short-lived ones. Accordingly, when a tracked item remains absent for an increasing number of time windows, it becomes progressively more likely to be evicted. By explicitly incorporating this temporal behaviour into its replacement strategy, LASSO provides stronger protection for long-lived items. Moreover, LASSO can be naturally extended to the task of long-lived item detection with minimal modification, for which we introduce a new variant, LASSO-LL.

We further develop a formal analytical model for LASSO and derive theoretical error bounds that provide insight into its performance and reliability. Extensive evaluations across CPUs, Tofino programmable switches, and FPGAs using realistic traces demonstrate the effectiveness and robustness of LASSO under practical constraints. The results show that LASSO consistently outperforms the state of the art, achieving over a 5× improvement in F1 score compared to PSSketch [31] under limited memory budgets (e.g., 32 KB). Moreover, LASSO incurs only modest resource overhead on both programmable switches and FPGAs, underscoring its lightweight design and deployability in resource-constrained environments.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Formal Definition

► **Data Stream.** A data stream \mathcal{S} is modeled as a sequence of key-value pairs (k_i, v_i) , where each key $k_i \in \mathcal{U}$ uniquely identifies an item from the universe \mathcal{U} and the corresponding value v_i stores statistics associated with that item. In network monitoring applications, keys typically denote flow identifiers, such as source IP addresses, while values maintain flow-level statistics.

► **Time Windows.** The stream \mathcal{S} is divided into consecutive, non-overlapping time windows. Let W denote the total number of time windows, indexed by $w = 1, 2, \dots, W$.

► **Frequency.** For an item $u \in \mathcal{U}$, its frequency, denoted by $f(u)$, is defined as the total number of occurrences of u in the entire data stream \mathcal{S} .

► **Persistence.** For an item $u \in \mathcal{U}$, its persistence, denoted by $p(u)$, is defined as the number of distinct time windows in which u appears at least once. By definition, each time window contributing to $p(u)$ contains at least one occurrence of u , which implies the following relation: $f(u) \geq p(u), \forall u \in \mathcal{U}$.

► **Long-Lived Sparse Item.** Given a persistence threshold $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ and a sparsity parameter $\theta \geq 1$, an item $u \in \mathcal{U}$ is defined as a *long-lived sparse item* if it satisfies both of the following conditions: $p(u) \geq \alpha \cdot W$ and $f(u) \leq \theta \cdot p(u)$.

2.2 Hardware Platforms

2.2.1 Programmable Switches. Programmable switches have recently emerged as an important execution substrate for high-speed data processing tasks [17, 32]. By enabling customized packet processing logic in the data plane, these devices can operate directly on streaming data at line rate, making them particularly attractive for real-time analytics and monitoring applications. Their architecture typically separates the *data plane*, which performs per-packet processing at high speed, from the *control plane*, which handles management and configuration tasks at a much lower rate [16].

Despite their strong processing capabilities, programmable switches impose stringent constraints that fundamentally shape algorithm design. The data plane supports only a restricted set of simple operations, primarily integer arithmetic, comparisons, and bitwise logic, while more complex computations such as floating-point arithmetic or iterative control flow are largely not supported. In addition, packet processing is organized as a fixed pipeline with a limited number of stages. For instance, widely deployed switches such as Tofino-1 provide a bounded pipeline depth (e.g., 12 stages), with each stage offering only limited computation and state. Moreover, on-chip memory resources are tightly constrained [27]. These constraints make programmable switches a challenging platform for deploying sophisticated data stream analytics. At the same time, they provide a strong benchmark for practicality: *approaches that can operate within data-plane constraints are inherently lightweight and are more likely to generalize to other resource-constrained hardware platforms* [32].

2.2.2 FPGAs. FPGAs provide a flexible hardware platform for accelerating high-speed data processing by enabling custom computation pipelines to be instantiated directly in hardware [29]. Their ability to exploit fine-grained parallelism makes them well suited for streaming workloads. However, FPGA designs must operate under practical constraints, including limited on-chip resources and the high implementation cost of certain arithmetic operations, such as division, modulo, and non-linear computations, as well as complex control flow. As a result, sketch implementations on FPGAs typically require careful design to balance accuracy, resource usage, and processing efficiency.

2.3 Related Work

2.3.1 Frequency Estimation. This task focuses on estimating the frequency of individual items, which forms a fundamental building block for many heavy-item-based problems, such as heavy hitter and heavy changer detection [11, 22, 28, 37]. Count-Min Sketch (CMS) [5] is one of the most widely used solutions. CMS maintains

a two-dimensional array of counters with r rows and b columns, where each row is associated with an independent hash function. Upon item arrival, the key is hashed into one bucket per row and the corresponding counters are incremented. An item's frequency is estimated by taking the minimum value among these counters. More recent approaches, such as Stingy Sketch [13] and Pyramid Sketch [21], exploit hierarchical designs and dynamically adjust counter sizes based on observed frequencies. Other methods that employ dynamically sized counters include [1, 10, 25, 38]. However, the increased complexity of these designs makes them difficult to deploy on programmable switches. Moreover, most sketch-based frequency estimation techniques are tailored to identifying heavy items, which limits their ability to detect long-lived sparse items.

2.3.2 Long-Lived Item Detection. To detect long-lived (*persistent*) items, On-Off Sketch [36] introduces a flag mechanism to suppress duplicate updates within each time window. However, its coarse replacement strategy results in limited lookup accuracy, particularly under tight memory budgets. To improve accuracy, P-Sketch [18] and Pandora [14] augment each bucket with additional metadata to capture temporal information about item arrivals, offering stronger protection for potential long-lived items. Stable-Sketch [19] further introduces a bucket-stability metric to prioritize persistent items, but this improvement comes at the cost of increased memory consumption. As the number of long-lived items grows, fewer buckets can be maintained within a fixed memory budget, ultimately degrading detection accuracy. Moreover, these approaches rely on per-bucket flags to suppress duplicate updates, which poses practical challenges on programmable switches. In particular, flag management requires coordination between the data plane and the control plane, incurring additional communication overhead. Under high arrival rates, delayed flag resets can prevent timely updates, rendering these methods ineffective [16]. Although Pallas [16] partially mitigates this issue, it still relies on auxiliary offline tables to support probabilistic replacement, which reduces hardware friendliness and limits flexibility across deployment settings.

2.3.3 Long-Lived Sparse Item Detection. To detect this item pattern, a straightforward baseline is to combine CMS with On-Off Sketch, where CMS tracks item frequency and On-Off Sketch records persistence. However, such a combination incurs substantial memory overhead and limits processing throughput. PISketch [6] adopts a weight-based strategy in which an item's weight is increased by a predefined value L ($L > 1$) when it first appears in a time window, and subsequently decreased by one for each additional occurrence within the same window. An item is evicted once its weight drops to zero. While effective in principle, this approach is highly sensitive to the choice of L , and a fixed weight parameter struggles to adapt across diverse item distributions. PSSketch [31], the current state-of-the-art for detecting this pattern, further exploits the characteristics of long-lived sparse items by employing multi-layer designs with variable-length, bitwise counters. Although this design improves detection accuracy, it introduces significant processing overhead and complexity, which reduces throughput and renders the approach impractical for deployment on constrained hardware platforms such as programmable switches. These limitations motivate the design of a new approach, LASSO, that combines high accuracy and fast processing speed with practical, hardware-friendly deployability.

3 Lasso Design

3.1 Design Principles

To enable efficient detection under the strict constraints imposed by practical hardware, LASSO adopts a simple yet effective design guided by the following principles.

► **Design Principle 1: Timely Eviction of Non-Long-Lived Sparse Items.** Under tight memory budgets, hash collisions become frequent, making it essential to promptly remove items that are unlikely to be long-lived and sparse. Leveraging the defining property of long-lived sparse items, LASSO evaluates the relationship between frequency and persistence. Specifically, if a tracked item's frequency f is no smaller than $\theta \cdot p$, indicating that the item is not sufficiently sparse, the incoming item is permitted to evict the incumbent one. This eviction strategy prioritizes memory for more promising long-lived sparse candidates, improving detection effectiveness under constrained resources.

► **Design Principle 2: Prioritize Protection for Long-Lived Items.** Item distributions in real-world data streams are typically highly skewed, with the vast majority of items being short-lived [4]. Prior studies have shown that approximately 90% of items in realistic CAIDA traces [3] appear in no more than ten time windows [20]. Under such skewed distributions, long-lived items are particularly vulnerable to being evicted by the overwhelming number of short-lived ones. To address this challenge, LASSO incorporates temporal information about item arrivals: when a tracked item is absent for many consecutive time windows, its likelihood of being a genuine long-lived item decreases [14]. Leveraging this observation, LASSO provides stronger protection to potential long-lived items while gradually relaxing protection for stale ones. Importantly, this protection mechanism is achieved without introducing additional per-bucket metadata, in contrast to prior designs [14, 18, 19, 34], preserving memory efficiency.

► **Design Principle 3: Eliminating Data/Control-Plane Coordination.** Most existing approaches for detecting long-lived items rely on a flag-reset mechanism that clears per-bucket flags at the end of each time window. This design requires frequent coordination between the data plane and the control plane, which introduces communication overhead and can lead to inaccurate persistence tracking. Prior studies [16] have shown that when the item arrival rate reaches tens of Mbps, state-of-the-art flag-based schemes become ineffective on programmable switches due to delayed or untimely flag resets [17]. These observations require the complete removal of flag-based mechanisms when tracking long-lived sparse items.

► **Design Principle 4: Avoiding Probabilistic Replacement.** In addition, probabilistic replacement is widely adopted in sketch-based designs [11, 14, 19, 33, 34, 37], but such strategies typically depend on floating-point operations, including division or exponentiation. These operations are either unsupported or prohibitively expensive on practical hardware platforms, particularly programmable switches. To ensure efficient and reliable deployment, LASSO instead adopts a hardware-friendly replacement strategy that avoids probabilistic computation while maintaining effective eviction behavior.

3.2 Data Structure

Figure 1 illustrates the data structure of LASSO, which consists of r rows, each containing b columns (*buckets*). Each bucket maintains four fields. K stores the item key, such as a unique user identifier or a source IP address in network traffic. P records the item's persistence, capturing the number of time windows in which the item appears. W stores the index of the most recent time window in which the item was observed. This field enables LASSO to capture temporal information without relying on per-window flag resets, allowing the entire scheme to be implemented purely in the data plane of programmable switches [16]. The details are elaborated in Section 3.3. V records the item's frequency. LASSO adopts a flat bucket structure instead of a hierarchical design, reducing update complexity, improving throughput, and simplifying implementation on constrained hardware platforms [19].

Figure 1: Data structure of LASSO.

3.3 Main Operations

LASSO supports two core operations: (1) Update, which processes each incoming item and updates the sketch accordingly, and (2) Query, which retrieves items identified as long-lived and sparse.

3.3.1 Update. Algorithm 1 presents the update procedure of LASSO. Initially, all buckets are empty, with their key, persistence, last-arrival window, and frequency fields set to zero. A global counter C is maintained and incremented upon each item arrival. The current time window index is computed as $currentWindow = \lceil C/G \rceil$, where G denotes the predefined window size (Lines 1–4).

For each incoming item u , LASSO applies the r hash functions h_1, \dots, h_r iteratively to locate one candidate bucket per row (Lines 5–6). The update proceeds according to one of the following cases.

► **Case 1: Empty bucket.** If a hashed bucket is empty, the incoming item is inserted immediately (Lines 7–9). The key is set to $u.key$, persistence and frequency counters are initialized to one, and the last-arrival window is set to the current window. The update terminates once an empty bucket is found.

► **Case 2: Hit.** If the stored key matches the incoming item, the frequency counter is incremented (Lines 10–11). If the item has not appeared in the current window ($W_{v,q} < currentWindow$), the persistence counter is incremented once and the last-arrival window is updated (Lines 12–15). By recording the most recent window in which an item appears, the last-arrival window W ensures that persistence increases at most once per window, eliminating the need for per-window flag resets and enabling fully data-plane execution.

► **Case 3: Miss and candidate selection.** If all hashed buckets are occupied by different items, LASSO evaluates each bucket using a deviation metric $dev = V_{v,q} - \theta \cdot P_{v,q}$, which measures how far the tracked item deviates from the long-lived sparse property (Lines 16–17). The bucket with the largest deviation is selected as the replacement candidate (Lines 18–20). After candidate selection (Line 21), LASSO checks whether the selected bucket has already been updated in the current window. If so, the incoming item is discarded to avoid interfering with ongoing updates (Lines 22–23).

Algorithm 1: Update Procedure of LASSO

Input: incoming item u , hash functions h_1, \dots, h_r , global counter C , window size G , sparsity parameter θ , persistent threshold α

- 1 **Initialization:** For all buckets (v, q) , $K_{v,q} \leftarrow \emptyset$, $P_{v,q} \leftarrow 0$, $W_{v,q} \leftarrow 0$, $V_{v,q} \leftarrow 0$.
- 2 $C \leftarrow C + 1$
- 3 $currentWindow \leftarrow \lceil C/G \rceil$
- 4 $maxDev \leftarrow -\infty$, $cand \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 5 **for** $v = 1$ **to** r **do**
- 6 $q \leftarrow h_v(u.key)$
- 7 **if** $K_{v,q} = \emptyset$ **then**
- 8 $(K_{v,q}, P_{v,q}, W_{v,q}, V_{v,q}) \leftarrow (u.key, 1, currentWindow, 1)$
- 9 **return**
- 10 **else if** $K_{v,q} = u.key$ **then**
- 11 $V_{v,q} \leftarrow V_{v,q} + 1$
- 12 **if** $W_{v,q} < currentWindow$ **then**
- 13 $P_{v,q} \leftarrow P_{v,q} + 1$
- 14 $W_{v,q} \leftarrow currentWindow$
- 15 **return**
- 16 **else**
- 17 $dev \leftarrow V_{v,q} - \theta \cdot P_{v,q}$
- 18 **if** $dev > maxDev$ **then**
- 19 $maxDev \leftarrow dev$
- 20 $cand \leftarrow (v, q)$
- 21 **Let** $cand = (v^*, q^*)$
- 22 **if** $W_{v^*,q^*} \geq currentWindow$ **then**
- 23 **return**
- 24 $dev \leftarrow V_{v^*,q^*} - \theta \cdot P_{v^*,q^*}$
- // Replace non-sparse item
- 25 **if** $dev > 0$ **then**
- 26 $(K_{v^*,q^*}, P_{v^*,q^*}, W_{v^*,q^*}, V_{v^*,q^*}) \leftarrow (u.key, 1, currentWindow, 1)$
- 27 **return**
- 28 $pThresh \leftarrow \alpha \cdot currentWindow$
- 29 **if** $P_{v^*,q^*} \geq pThresh$ **then**
- 30 **return**
- 31 $gap \leftarrow currentWindow - W_{v^*,q^*}$
- 32 **if** $gap > P_{v^*,q^*}$ **then**
- 33 $P_{v^*,q^*} \leftarrow \max(P_{v^*,q^*} - 1, 0)$
- 34 $V_{v^*,q^*} \leftarrow \max(V_{v^*,q^*} - 1, 0)$
- 35 **if** $P_{v^*,q^*} = 0$ **then**
- 36 $(K_{v^*,q^*}, P_{v^*,q^*}, W_{v^*,q^*}, V_{v^*,q^*}) \leftarrow (u.key, 1, currentWindow, 1)$

If the deviation is positive, indicating that the item is insufficiently sparse, it is immediately replaced by the incoming item (Lines 24–27). Otherwise, the item is treated as a potential long-lived sparse candidate. A dynamic persistence threshold $pThresh = \alpha \cdot currentWindow$ is computed (Line 28). If the item's persistence exceeds this threshold, the update terminates to preserve on-track long-lived items (Lines 29–30). For remaining items, temporal staleness is considered. If the number of consecutive windows in which the item is absent exceeds its persistence, both persistence and frequency counters are decayed (Lines 31–34). Once the persistence reaches zero, the bucket is reclaimed and updated with the incoming item (Lines 35–36).

Overall, the update procedure prioritizes long-lived sparse items, promptly evicts non-promising candidates, and relies only on simple arithmetic and comparisons, making Lasso lightweight and suitable for deployment on constrained hardware.

3.3.2 Query. To identify long-lived sparse items, LASSO performs a linear scan over all buckets and reports an item u if its persistence $p(u) \geq \alpha W$ and its frequency $f(u) \leq \theta \cdot p(u)$.

3.4 Extension to Long-Lived Item Detection

LASSO extends naturally to long-lived item detection via a variant, LASSO-LL, which maintains only the item key, persistence, and last arrival window index, and eliminates all sparsity-related computations. During updates, if hash collisions occur in all rows, LASSO-LL selects the bucket with the smallest value across rows and checks whether the tracked item has already appeared in the current time window. If so, the incoming item is discarded. Otherwise, LASSO-LL compares the item’s persistence against a dynamic threshold, $\alpha \cdot \text{currentWindow}$. If the persistence meets or exceeds this threshold, the item is preserved; otherwise, it decays according to the absence gap, as in LASSO. The bucket is reclaimed and replaced by the incoming item only when the persistence drops to zero.

4 Formal Analysis

First, we present that LASSO incurs only one-sided estimation errors: for any item u , the estimated persistence $\hat{p}(u)$ and frequency $\hat{f}(u)$ never exceed their true values $p(u)$ and $f(u)$. We formalize this as Theorem A.1 and defer its statement and proof to Appendix A.1.

Next, we show that LASSO achieves a low error rate in identifying long-lived sparse items, and the analysis provides practical guidance on selecting memory sizes to bound underestimation errors below a desired threshold.

THEOREM 4.1. *Define the persistence underestimation random variable $X(u) := p - \hat{p}(u)$. Then the probability that LASSO fails to identify the long-lived sparse item u satisfies:*

$$\Pr[\text{FN}(u)] \leq 2 \exp\left(-\tau^* \log \frac{\tau^*}{\bar{\mu}} + \tau^* - \bar{\mu}\right)$$

$\bar{\mu} = \frac{W\Omega r}{b} \left(1 - e^{-\lambda t} + 2e^{-\lambda t - \frac{\lambda t}{4}}\right) + W e^{-\lambda t}$, $\tau^* = \min\left\{\epsilon \alpha W, \frac{\epsilon \alpha W}{\theta - 1}\right\}$. Here, α is the persistence threshold, θ is the sparsity parameter, W is the total number of time windows, r is the number of sketch rows, b is the number of buckets per row, n is the number of distinct items, λ is the Poisson arrival rate, t is the window length, and $\epsilon > 0$ is a margin parameter. Moreover, $\Omega := 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{b}\right)^{n-1}$ denotes the per-row collision probability under uniform hashing.

PROOF. The proof is provided in Supplemental Material [15]. \square

Finally, we establish that LASSO-LL satisfies the (ϵ, δ) -counting guarantee [16, 19], demonstrating a low error rate in long-lived-item identification.

THEOREM 4.2. *Given a small positive number ϵ , the probability of LASSO-LL failing to identify a persistent flow is upper bounded by $\delta = \frac{\Omega r}{\epsilon b} \left(\zeta^2 + \frac{(n-1)\lambda t}{r} e^{-3\lambda t - D(\alpha\|\zeta)}\right)$, where $\zeta := 1 - e^{-\lambda t}$ and $D(\alpha\|\zeta) = \alpha \ln \frac{\alpha}{\zeta} + (1-\alpha) \ln \frac{1-\alpha}{1-\zeta}$. The remaining symbols are defined as in Theorem 4.1.*

PROOF. The proof can be found in Appendix A.2. \square

5 Implementation

We implement LASSO on three representative platforms: x86 CPU, Intel Tofino, and Xilinx FPGA. This section shows that LASSO can be efficiently deployed on both general-purpose and specialized hardware, followed by platform-specific implementation details.

5.1 CPU Platform

We implement LASSO and all baseline algorithms in C++ on a general-purpose CPU platform, using MurmurHash for item hashing. Experiments are conducted on a machine equipped with an Intel Core i5-1135G7 CPU (2.40 GHz) and 16 GB of DRAM, running Ubuntu 20.04.

5.2 Tofino Programmable Switch

LASSO is implemented on a Wedge 100BF-32X programmable switch by using P4 language [2]. As shown in Figure 2, LASSO organizes a row of buckets realized by four register arrays, K , P , W , and V . Specifically, K stores the flow key (the packet’s source IP address), P maintains a persistence counter, W records the window counter, and V tracks the flow frequency.

Figure 2: LASSO’s Tofino workflow.

On each packet arrival, the ingress pipeline first computes a bucket index using a CRC-based hash over the flow key and reads the corresponding row state ($K/P/W/V$). It then checks whether the stored key matches the incoming key and derives the per-packet update decision (e.g., refreshing the current bucket or selecting it for replacement). Finally, the pipeline computes the updated counter values for P , W , and V according to LASSO’s update rules.

Implementing this read–compute–write sequence must respect the switch’s hardware constraint that a packet can access a given register resource at most once per pipeline pass. To accommodate this limitation, we split the operation into two passes using packet recirculation. The first pass performs the state read and computes the update decision, after which the packet is looped back to the ingress pipeline for a second pass that commits the modified values to K , P , W , and V . We use the switch’s built-in loopback port for recirculation, ensuring the additional pass remains internal and does not consume bandwidth on any external port.

5.3 FPGA

We implement LASSO with two rows on a Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC FPGA (XCZU2EG), mapping its data-plane operations onto a streaming hardware datapath. The design follows a fixed read–modify–write pipeline, enabling continuous processing of incoming items with deterministic execution.

The datapath is organized as a sequence of pipeline stages. Upon arrival, the input item key is parsed and distributed to parallel hash units to compute the storage indices for the two rows. These indices are then used to access the corresponding bucket entries stored in on-chip memory. Each bucket maintains a compact state record consisting of the item key, persistence counter, last-arrival window, and frequency counter, which are read into pipeline registers.

The retrieved bucket states are fed into a reconfigurable update logic stage that instantiates the update policy of LASSO. This stage jointly examines the two candidate buckets by comparing their

Figure 3: Long-Lived sparse item detection F1 score with different algorithms, as a function of memory size.

Figure 4: Long-Lived sparse item detection ARE with different algorithms, as a function of memory size.

Figure 5: Update speed in long-lived sparse item detection with different algorithms, as a function of memory size.

deviation metrics to select a replacement candidate on a miss, and determines whether the incoming item triggers a replacement. To ensure efficient hardware realization, all real-valued computations in Lasso are translated into fixed-point form. In particular, comparisons involving the sparsity parameter are rewritten as scaled integer inequalities and implemented using shift-and-add logic, allowing the update logic to rely solely on simple arithmetic operations and comparisons, without floating-point units, multipliers, or division operators. The updated bucket records are written back to on-chip memory, completing the read–modify–write sequence.

6 Evaluation Setup

► **Traces.** Following prior work [14, 25, 37], we evaluate LASSO using realistic traces from CAIDA [3]. These traces serve as representative large-scale data streams with highly skewed item distributions, a characteristic common to many real-world stream analytics tasks. We randomly select traces from four years (2015, 2016, 2018, and 2019), comprising 20.2M packets from 520K items, 22.3M packets from 730K items, 22.3M packets from 760K items, and 29.5M packets from 1.53M items, respectively. The source IP address is used as the item key [31]. *In addition to the CAIDA traces, results on additional datasets are reported in Section 7.3.*

► **Parameter Settings.** We set the number of rows (r) in LASSO to 2, following prior work [17, 37]. For each trace, traffic is partitioned into 100 time windows with the threshold α fixed at 0.4, while θ is varied from 1.1 to 1.3 to evaluate robustness. Table 1 reports the number of ground-truth long-lived sparse items across different traces under varying values of the sparsity threshold θ . As shown, smaller θ values make detection more challenging, as the number of qualifying items becomes very limited. Overall, long-lived sparse items constitute only a small fraction of each trace, highlighting the

highly skewed nature of the underlying data distribution. We further evaluate the performance of LASSO under additional parameter settings, with detailed results provided in Section A.3.

Table 1: Number of ground-truth long-lived sparse items under different θ values.

Trace	$\theta = 1.1$	$\theta = 1.2$	$\theta = 1.3$
CAIDA 2015	41	86	163
CAIDA 2016	270	465	791
CAIDA 2018	79	193	367
CAIDA 2019	181	349	603

► **Baselines.** (i) We compare LASSO with the state-of-the-art approach for long-lived sparse item lookup, PSSketch [31]. Although other methods exist for this task (e.g., PISketch [6]), we omit them from the comparison since PSSketch substantially improves both processing speed and accuracy. Comparisons with earlier baselines therefore provide limited additional insight. (ii) For long-lived item lookup, we compare LASSO-LL with the state-of-the-art schemes Pandora [14], Stable-Sketch [19], and Tight-Sketch [20]. For a fair comparison, the number of rows in all baselines is set to 2, consistent with LASSO-LL.

► **Metrics.** We evaluate LASSO using the following metrics: (1) *F1 score*, defined as the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, where Precision is the fraction of reported long-lived sparse items that are correct and Recall is the fraction of ground-truth long-lived sparse items that are successfully detected; (2) *Average Relative Error (ARE)*, defined as $ARE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{\hat{u}_i - u_i}{u_i} \right|$, where u_i and \hat{u}_i denote the ground-truth value and the estimated value, respectively; and (3) *Update speed*, measured in millions of operations per second (Mops), to evaluate the processing throughput. Each experiment is repeated five times, and the average result is reported [17].

Figure 6: Long-Lived item detection F1 score with different algorithms, as a function of memory size.

Figure 7: Long-Lived item detection ARE with different algorithms, as a function of memory size.

Figure 8: Update speed in long-lived item detection with different algorithms, as a function of memory size.

Figure 9: F1 score under different parameter settings.

7 Trace-Driven Evaluation

7.1 Long-Lived Sparse Item Lookup

Figures 3–5 compare the detection accuracy and update speed of different schemes under varying memory budgets and sparsity thresholds θ . Here, we vary the memory size from 16 KB to 256 KB [11, 14, 19]. As shown in Figure 3, LASSO consistently achieves higher F1 scores than PSSketch under constrained memory settings (16–128 KB) across different values of θ . For example, when $\theta = 1.1$ and the memory budget is 32 KB, LASSO improves the F1 score over PSSketch by 234.5%, 526.18%, 281.07%, and 267.39% on the CAIDA 2015, 2016, 2018, and 2019 traces, respectively. This performance advantage stems from the dedicated update design of LASSO, which effectively preserves long-lived sparse items in

the presence of severe hash collisions, preventing them from being incorrectly evicted by a large number of non-promising items. When the memory budget increases to 256 KB, where hash collisions are less severe, PSSketch attains higher detection accuracy. This is primarily due to its complex multi-level counter design with heterogeneous counter sizes, which enables more effective memory utilization. However, the resulting operational complexity leads to substantially lower update speed, while also making PSSketch difficult to deploy in practice.

Figure 4 reports the estimation accuracy of item sparsity, defined as the ratio between an item’s frequency and persistence [31]. As shown, LASSO consistently achieves substantially lower estimation errors than PSSketch across all evaluated settings.

Figure 5 presents the update speed of different schemes. Owing to its simple yet effective design, LASSO achieves significantly higher update throughput than PSSketch. For instance, when $\theta = 1.3$, the average update speed of LASSO is 169.67%, 182.5%, 160.94%, and 163.48% higher than that of PSSketch on the CAIDA 2015, 2016, 2018, and 2019 traces, respectively.

7.2 Long-Lived Item Lookup

Figures 6–7 compare the detection accuracy of LASSO-LL with the considered baselines. As shown in Figure 6, LASSO-LL consistently achieves the highest F1 score across all memory settings. On average, LASSO-LL improves detection accuracy by 12.03%, 16.81%, 13.03%, and 14.3% over the competitive scheme Pandora on the CAIDA 2015, 2016, 2018, and 2019 traces, respectively. This performance advantage stems from the fine-grained protection mechanism that preserves long-lived items under hash collisions. As

further illustrated in Figure 7, LASSO-LL significantly reduces estimation error compared with existing approaches. Finally, Figure 8 shows that LASSO-LL achieves update speeds comparable to the baselines. Overall, these results show the effectiveness of LASSO-LL.

To further evaluate the robustness of LASSO-LL under different parameter settings, we first fix the memory budget to 16 KB and set the persistence threshold α to 0.4, while varying the number of time windows W from 500 to 1,700. As shown in Figure 9(a), LASSO-LL consistently achieves the highest F1 score across all window settings. We then fix the number of windows to $W = 500$ and vary the persistence threshold α from 0.3 to 0.8. Figure 9(b) shows that LASSO-LL maintains superior detection accuracy compared to the baselines across all threshold values. Overall, these results demonstrate the robustness of LASSO-LL to variations in key parameters.

7.3 Detection Accuracy on Additional Traces

Beyond the CAIDA traces, we further evaluate the effectiveness of our approach using additional synthetic traces. Following prior work [25], we generate three traces based on Zipf distributions with skewness values of 0.15, 0.4, and 0.6, denoted as #1, #2, and #3, respectively. Trace #1 contains 30M entries from 0.3M items, trace #2 contains 15M entries from 0.45M items, and trace #3 contains 20M entries from 0.4M items. Each trace is divided into 100 time windows, with the persistence threshold α fixed at 0.4 and the sparsity threshold θ set to 1.3. Under these settings, the numbers of ground-truth long-lived sparse items are 603, 1,152, and 728 for traces #1, #2, and #3, respectively.

Figure 10: Detection accuracy in long-lived sparse item detection with different traces.

Figure 10 compares the detection accuracy of LASSO and PSSketch on these traces. As shown, LASSO consistently achieves higher F1 scores and lower estimation errors across all traces. These results further demonstrate the robustness and effectiveness of LASSO.

Figure 11: Detection accuracy in long-lived item detection with different traces.

We further compare the performance of LASSO-LL with the considered baselines on the long-lived item lookup task. We fix the total number of time windows to $W = 100$ and the persistence threshold to $\alpha = 0.4$. Under this configuration, the numbers of ground-truth long-lived items in traces #1, #2, and #3 are 13,682, 18,538, and 10,661, respectively. Notably, these counts are substantially larger than those of long-lived sparse items, highlighting the increased difficulty of identifying the latter.

Figure 11 presents the detection accuracy for long-lived item lookup. As shown, LASSO-LL consistently achieves the highest F1 scores and the lowest persistence estimation errors compared with existing approaches. On average, LASSO-LL improves the F1 score by 9.58%, 17.41%, and 16.81% over Stable-Sketch on traces #1, #2, and #3, respectively.

7.4 SIMD Optimization

Although LASSO already achieves higher update speed than the state-of-the-art PSSketch, its performance can be further improved using SIMD (Single Instruction, Multiple Data) instructions to better accommodate high-speed data streams on CPU platforms. In particular, we adopt SIMD-friendly implementations to accelerate key comparison and bucket update operations, reducing per-item processing overhead while keeping identical algorithmic semantics.

Figure 12 presents the update speed of LASSO with and without SIMD optimization under different traces and memory configurations. The results show that SIMD optimization consistently delivers noticeable performance gains. On average, the update speed is improved by 20.63%, 15.63%, 10.51%, and 16.91% on the CAIDA 2015, 2016, 2018, and 2019 traces, respectively.

8 Hardware Evaluation

8.1 Tofino Programmable Switch

Programmable switches operate under strict resource constraints, making efficient resource utilization critical for data streaming

Figure 12: Lasso’s update speed w/wo SIMD optimization.

applications. We evaluate the hardware resource footprint of LASSO using the Intel P4 Insight analysis tool [12].

As summarized in Table 2, LASSO exhibits a compact hardware footprint on the Tofino switch, consuming only a small fraction of the available on-chip resources. The design makes lightweight use of hash units, with hash-bit utilization limited to 3.99%, indicating minimal pressure on the hashing pipeline. Although LASSO relies on exact-match tables and stateful registers to maintain per-item metadata, the overall SRAM utilization remains low at only 3.75%. Since no ternary matching is required, TCAM resources are not consumed. The conditional update logic introduced by control-flow operations results in a gateway utilization of 20.83%. In addition, LASSO incurs limited pressure on match crossbars (5.08%) and VLIW instruction slots (6.77%), leaving substantial headroom for co-locating other data-plane applications on the same switch pipeline. Consistent with this low overall resource footprint, LASSO is implemented using 10 pipeline stages on Tofino, fitting within the available pipeline depth without requiring any architectural modifications.

Table 2: Resource Usage of Lasso in Tofino Switch.

Resource	Usage	Resource	Usage
Hash Bit	3.99%	Match Crossbars	5.08%
Gateways	20.83%	Logical Table ID	23.96%
VLIW Instruction	6.77%	SRAM	3.75%
Stages Used		10	

Next, we use the CAIDA 2019 trace to evaluate the detection accuracy of LASSO on the programmable switch. The trace is divided into 1,400 time windows, the persistence threshold is set to 0.4, and the sparsity threshold θ is varied from 1.1 to 1.4. We further vary the number of buckets from 1,024 to 16,384 [29]. Existing baselines such as PSSketch are omitted from this experiment, as their complex designs make them impractical for deployment on programmable switches. As shown in Figure 13, LASSO consistently maintains high detection accuracy across all configurations. Notably, even under a highly constrained setting with only 1,024 buckets, LASSO achieves an F1 score of at least 0.8. These results demonstrate that LASSO is both effective and well suited for practical deployment on programmable switching hardware.

8.2 FPGA

Table 3 summarizes the resource utilization of LASSO on FPGA. The design incurs a negligible logic footprint, consuming only 11 Look-Up Tables (LUTs) and 25 flip-flops, which corresponds to less than 0.04% of the available logic resources on the target device. The I/O utilization accounts for 20 bonded I/O pins, representing around

Figure 13: Lasso’s detection accuracy on the Tofino switch. 8% of the available I/O resources. This small resource footprint enables efficient co-location with other FPGA-resident workloads. Moreover, based on post-route timing analysis, the FPGA implementation achieves a maximum clock frequency of 666.7 MHz while sustaining one item per cycle, corresponding to a peak throughput of 666.7 Mops. Overall, these results show that LASSO enables high-throughput streaming execution on FPGA with limited overhead.

Table 3: FPGA resource utilization of Lasso.

Metric	Value	Available	Utilization (%)
Look-Up Tables (LUTs)	11	47,232	0.02
Flip-flops (FFs)	25	94,464	0.03
I/O pins	20	252	7.94

9 Conclusion

In this paper, we study the problem of detecting long-lived sparse items in high-speed data streams, a pattern that is both practically important and challenging to capture under tight memory constraints. We present LASSO, a lightweight and efficient mechanism that jointly leverages item persistence and frequency to accurately distinguish long-lived sparse behaviour from transient noise. By relying on simple update logic and avoiding heavyweight operations, Lasso supports high-throughput stream processing while remaining practical to deploy on modern data-processing platforms. Extensive evaluations on real-world traces, together with implementations on CPU, programmable switches, and FPGAs, demonstrate that Lasso consistently achieves strong detection accuracy and throughput across a wide range of memory budgets with low resource overhead. The source code of Lasso is available at [15].

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Appendix

A.1 Proof of Theorem A.1

THEOREM A.1 (NO OVERESTIMATION ERROR). *For any item u in a data stream \mathcal{S} , let $p(u)$ and $f(u)$ denote the true persistence and frequency of u , respectively, and let $\hat{p}(u)$ and $\hat{f}(u)$ denote the corresponding estimates maintained by LASSO. Then, at all times, $\hat{p}(u) \leq p(u)$, $\hat{f}(u) \leq f(u)$.*

PROOF. The proof is conducted using induction over the sequence of item arrivals. The base case $\hat{p}_0(u) \leq p_0(u)$ and $\hat{f}_0(u) \leq f_0(u)$ holds at $t = 0$ because all fields in bucket are set to zero, prior to observing any item. Assume the inequality holds at step x . At step $x + 1$, if the arriving item $u' \neq u$, LASSO may evict u or decay its counters or remain its counter unchanged, thus we have $\hat{p}_{x+1}(u) \leq \hat{p}_x(u) \leq p_x(u) = p_{x+1}(u)$ and $\hat{f}_{x+1}(u) \leq \hat{f}_x(u) \leq f_x(u) = f_{x+1}(u)$. If $u' = u$, The estimator $\hat{f}_{x+1}(u)$ either increments (if hit), or record as 1 (if inserted/replaced), or becomes 0 (if rejected), and $\hat{p}_{x+1}(u)$ except above change, it may remain unchanged. In all cases, the estimator $\hat{f}_{x+1}(u)$ increases by at most 1, so $\hat{f}_{x+1}(u) \leq \hat{f}_x(u) + 1 \leq f_x(u) + 1 \leq f_{x+1}(u)$ and the estimator $\hat{p}_{x+1}(u)$, we have $\hat{p}_{x+1}(u) \leq p_{x+1}(u)$.

In all cases, we have shown that if the property holds at x , it also holds at $x + 1$. By induction, it follows that for all $t \geq 0$ and for every item u , $\hat{p}_t(u) \leq p_t(u)$, $\hat{f}_t(u) \leq f_t(u)$. Hence, the theorem holds at all steps, guaranteeing that the estimated persistency and frequency never exceeds its true value. Consequently, LASSO incurs only one-sided underestimation errors. \square

A.2 Proof of Theorem 4.2

PROOF. Consider a persistent item u . When u arrives and is mapped to a bucket $B(v, q)$ already occupied by a different item $u' \neq u$, the persistent value of this bucket in LASSO-LL is either unchanged, decreased by 1, or reset to 1.

We adopt the standard assumption in persistent-item detection [16, 19]: once a persistent item u_i is mapped into a bucket; it remains in that bucket until the detection process completes.

Let T denote the (random) window in which item u is first successfully placed into the sketch. We decompose the underestimation $X(u)$ into two parts:

- Δ_1 : the number of windows before T in which u appears but is not inserted into any bucket;
- Δ_2 : the number of windows at or after T in which the persistence counter of u is decreased due to collision-triggered replacement attempts.

By one-sided error, no overestimation occurs, and therefore

$$\hat{p}(u) = p(u) - \Delta_1 - \Delta_2, \quad X(u) = \Delta_1 + \Delta_2.$$

Applying Markov's inequality for any $\epsilon > 0$:

$$\Pr(|p(u) - \hat{p}(u)| \geq \epsilon W) = \Pr(\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 \geq \epsilon W) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[\Delta_1 + \Delta_2]}{\epsilon W} \quad (1)$$

For each item u , the probability that in each of the r arrays, in one time window, there are hash collisions in the bucket to which item e is mapped:

$$\Pr\left(\bigcap_{u' \in \mathcal{S} \setminus \{u\}} \{h_v(u) = h_v(u')\}\right) \leq \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{b}\right)^{n-1}\right]^r \triangleq \Omega^r \quad (2)$$

Where n is the number of distinct items.

We assume all item follows a Poisson process with rate $\lambda > 0$ as a generally assumption in [16]. Time is partitioned into consecutive windows of equal length $t > 0$. For item u' , which occupied the bucket the item u choose to replace, For each window $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, L\}$, define the indicator variable

$$I_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{at least one packet of } u' \text{ arrives in window } i, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let

$$S_T = \sum_{i=1}^T I_i$$

denote the number of windows u' arrived among the previous T windows. For a single window, the probability of observing at least one arrival is

$$\zeta = \Pr(I_i = 1) = 1 - e^{-\lambda t}.$$

Thus S_T is a binomial random variable:

$$S_T \sim \text{Binomial}(T, \zeta), \quad \mathbb{E}[S_T] = \zeta T.$$

Define the random variable G to be the gap (measured in number of windows) between the current window T and the most recent previous window that u' appears:

$$G := T - \max\{i \leq T : I_i = 1\}.$$

Then G is geometrically distributed with parameter ζ :

$$\Pr(G = k) = (1 - \zeta)^k \zeta, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Let P_a be the probability that u hashes into a bucket occupied with item u' but fails to replace it. Based on the LASSO's replacement rule, we have:

$$P_a \leq \frac{\Omega^r}{b} \left(1 - e^{-\lambda t}\right). \quad (3)$$

Let $X_{0,T}(u)$ be the number of windows before T in which u appeared at least once. Since u follows a Poisson process with rate λ , we have:

$$\mathbb{E}[X_{0,j}(u)] = T(1 - \Pr(N(t) = 0)) = T(1 - e^{-\lambda t})$$

Hence we have:

$$\mathbb{E}[\Delta_1] = P_a \cdot \mathbb{E}[X_{0,j}(u)] \leq \frac{T\Omega^r}{b} \left(1 - e^{-\lambda t}\right)^2. \quad (4)$$

Now, we bound the expected number of collision-induced decrements *after* u has entered a bucket $\mathbb{E}[\Delta_2]$. After item u enters the bucket, based on LASSO, in each such window, at most one successful collision-induced replacement can decrease the persistence count of u by 1. And the bucket of u is chosen at random $\frac{1}{r}$.

We define the gap random variable H (in number of windows) between the current window W_c and the most recent *previous* window no earlier than T in which u' appears as

$$H \triangleq W_c - \max\{i \in \{T, T+1, \dots, W_c\} : I_i = 1\},$$

with the convention that if $I_i = 0$ for all $i \in \{T, T+1, \dots, W_c\}$, then

$$H \triangleq W_c - T + 1.$$

$$\Pr(H = k) = (1 - \zeta)^k \zeta, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Hence,

$$\Pr(H > 0) = 1 - \Pr(H = 0) = 1 - \zeta = e^{-\lambda t}.$$

Let P_b be the probability that a distinct item u' hashes into the same bucket as u , and make the count reduce by 1:

$$P_b \leq \frac{\Omega^r e^{-\lambda t}}{rb} \cdot \Pr(H > 0) \Pr(p(u) < pThresh) \Pr(p(u) < H). \quad (5)$$

Since $p(u) \sim \text{Binomial}(W_c, \zeta)$, for $pThresh = \alpha W_c$,

$$\Pr(p(u) < pThresh) = \Pr(p(u) < \alpha W_c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lceil \alpha W_c \rceil - 1} \binom{W_c}{k} \zeta^k (1-\zeta)^{W_c-k}.$$

Moreover, if $\alpha < \zeta$ (i.e., the threshold is below the mean), the Chernoff bound yields

$$\Pr(p(u) < \alpha W_c) \leq \exp(-W_c D(\alpha \parallel \zeta)),$$

where $D(\alpha \parallel \zeta) = \alpha \ln(\alpha/\zeta) + (1-\alpha) \ln((1-\alpha)/(1-\zeta))$.

Thus,

$$P_b \leq \frac{\Omega^r}{rb} \exp^{-2\lambda t - D(\alpha \parallel \zeta)}. \quad (6)$$

For each window W_i with $i \in \{X, \dots, W\}$, define the indicator $I_i = 1$ if at least one such collision (that decreases the counter of e_i) occurs in that window, and $I_i = 0$ otherwise. Then

$$\Delta_2 = \sum_{i=X}^{L-1} I_i, \quad \mathbb{E}[\Delta_2] = \sum_{i=X}^{L-1} \mathbb{E}[I_i].$$

In each window, the total expected number of arrivals from the $n-1$ other items is $(n-1)\lambda t$, and arrivals that both collide with e_i 's bucket and trigger a decrement are (stochastically) dominated by a Poisson random variable with mean $(n-1)\lambda t P_b$. Hence

$$\Pr(I_i = 1) = 1 - e^{-(n-1)\lambda t P_b}.$$

Based on the algorithm, when a collision happens, e_i must not have appeared in the same window. The probability is $e^{-\lambda t}$. Then, for each window W_i from T to W , the expectation that at least one such collision occurs is:

$$\mathbb{E}[\Delta_2] = \sum_{i=T}^{W-1} \mathbb{E}[I_i] \leq (W-T) e^{-\lambda t} (1 - \exp(-(n-1)\lambda t P_b)).$$

Using $1 - e^{-x} \leq x$, we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}[\Delta_2] \leq (W-T) \frac{(n-1)\lambda t}{rb} \Omega^r \exp(-3\lambda t - D(\alpha \parallel \zeta)).$$

Combining both parts:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(|p(u) - \hat{p}(u)| \leq \epsilon W) &\leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[\Delta_1 + \Delta_2]}{\epsilon W} \\ &\leq \frac{\Omega^r}{\epsilon} \left(\frac{T}{W} \cdot \frac{\zeta^2}{b} + \frac{W-T}{W} \cdot \frac{(n-1)\lambda t}{rb} e^{-3\lambda t - D(\alpha \parallel \zeta)} \right) \\ &\leq \frac{\Omega^r}{\epsilon b} \left(\zeta^2 + \frac{(n-1)\lambda t}{r} e^{-3\lambda t - D(\alpha \parallel \zeta)} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega &\triangleq 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{b}\right)^{n-1} \\ \zeta &\triangleq 1 - e^{-\lambda t} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$D(\alpha \parallel \zeta) = \alpha \ln \frac{\alpha}{\zeta} + (1-\alpha) \ln \frac{1-\alpha}{1-\zeta}. \quad \square$$

A.3 Detection Accuracy of Long-Lived Sparse Items under Different Thresholds

Here, we vary the thresholds to evaluate the robustness of LASSO. The trace is divided into 200 time windows, with the persistence threshold α fixed at 0.2, while the sparsity threshold θ varies from 1.1 to 1.3. We use the CAIDA 2019 trace for this experiment. Under this setting, the number of ground-truth long-lived sparse items is 767, 1,568, and 2,359 for $\theta = 1.1, 1.2,$ and 1.3 , respectively.

Figure 14 compares the F1 score and ARE of LASSO and PSSketch. As shown, LASSO consistently achieves higher detection accuracy. In particular, LASSO improves the F1 score over PSSketch by 57.46%, 45.69%, and 47.88% for sparsity thresholds $\theta = 1.1, 1.2,$ and 1.3 , respectively. In addition, LASSO attains substantially lower estimation error in sparsity estimation. Similar trends are observed under other parameter settings. These results confirm the robustness and effectiveness of our approach.

Figure 14: Detection accuracy of long-lived sparse items under different threshold settings.